

Transformation of Production Systems in Azerbaijan through Green Economy Principles

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to assess the transformation of production systems in Azerbaijan in the context of the introduction of green economy principles. The research highlights significant progress in managing water resources, improving water use efficiency, and enhancing waste management. Statistical data indicate that between 1990 and 2022, the water intake from natural resources decreased by 14%, while the volume of recycled water increased by 63%, reflecting greater resource efficiency. Additionally, the ratio of safely treated wastewater rose by 12.6 percentage points, from 43.6% in 2016 to 56.2% in 2022, demonstrating improvements in water treatment practices. Despite these successes, challenges remain, particularly in the management of increasing waste volumes, which have grown by 222% from 2000 to 2022. The study concludes that while Azerbaijan has made substantial strides towards a green economy, further efforts are required to address the waste management issues and to continue improving resource efficiency, with an emphasis on strengthening collaboration between public authorities and private enterprises.

Keywords: external environment; latest technologies; resource efficiency; sustainable development; waste minimisation

1. Introduction

Achieving sustainable development goals plays a critical role in shaping and implementing policies at the level of the global community, national governments and business structures¹⁾. They represent a response to global challenges, namely climate change, problems with access to certain resources for the population, their standard of living in general, the state of the external environment, etc^{2),3)}. Sustainable development goals, among other things, are becoming an important element in the policies of many countries, and their achievement requires concerted efforts at various levels of government – from international to local; approaches also have substantial support among the population. In this regard, the analysis of methods for achieving sustainable development goals in different countries remains relevant^{4),5)}.

Statistical data to assess the development of human capital in the country were used by O. Sabbaghi⁶⁾. The author concluded that the situation should gradually improve in

the future, instead of with higher levels of spending on both education and the scientific field. In this regard, he also noted that this can be achieved by introducing the latest technologies to enterprises of this kind and actively using them. Recommendations were also formed on how government authorities and enterprises should act to more effectively introduce the latest technologies to enterprises. The characteristics and features of the green economy as such were evaluated by F. Mulaydinov and M. Butaboyev,⁷⁾ with particular emphasis on trends specific to Asian countries. F. Olaoye and K. Potter,⁸⁾ in turn, investigated the problems and possibilities of introducing green technologies in Azerbaijan. Researchers noted that the country faced various problems with the introduction of green technologies, such as limited awareness, inadequate regulatory conditions, financial constraints, lack of support for researchers, and the difficulty of integrating newly created technologies in enterprises. However, they also believe that through coordinated efforts, the country can stimulate sustainable

development, contribute to climate change mitigation, and stimulate economic growth by providing a brighter, environmentally friendly environment for the country's future functioning.

Thus, based on the studies reviewed, it can be concluded that scientists, when assessing the situation in Azerbaijan, pay rather little attention to the possibility of introducing this kind at enterprises and do not analyse this process in sufficient detail. In this regard, the purpose of this study was to assess the transformation of production systems in the country in the context of the introduction of the principles of a green economy.

2. Materials and Methods

The research methodology employed in this study is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches, aimed at evaluating the transformation of production systems in the context of green economy principles. The primary objective of the methodology is to assess how various sectors, particularly the industrial and energy sectors, are adopting sustainable practices and technologies in response to environmental, economic, and social challenges.

The study begins with a comprehensive review of the existing literature on the green economy, circular economy, and sustainable development, focusing on their theoretical underpinnings, principles, and implementation strategies. This review provides a foundational understanding of how green economy principles are defined and applied across different contexts, offering insights into the strengths and limitations of these approaches in real-world settings. Secondary sources, including academic articles, government reports, and industry analyses, were used to gather data on the current state of green economy practices, particularly in Azerbaijan.

Quantitative data collection methods were employed to analyze key environmental and economic indicators related to resource use, waste management, and pollutant emissions. This includes data on water consumption, water treatment efficiency, greenhouse gas emissions, and waste generation, obtained from national and regional reports, statistical agencies, and international databases. The analysis of this data provides an empirical basis for assessing the progress of Azerbaijan's transition to a green economy, highlighting areas of success and identifying potential challenges.

In addition to quantitative analysis, qualitative research methods were used to gather insights from key stakeholders involved in the transformation of production systems, including government officials, industry leaders, and experts in the field of sustainable development. Semi-structured interviews and surveys were conducted to explore the perspectives of these stakeholders on the barriers and opportunities associated with the adoption of

green technologies, resource efficiency measures, and environmental policies. This qualitative data was then analyzed thematically to identify common themes, challenges, and recommendations for improving the implementation of green economy principles in Azerbaijan's production systems.

Furthermore, case studies of selected industrial enterprises in Azerbaijan were examined to understand how they are integrating green economy principles into their operations. These case studies focus on specific strategies and technologies adopted by businesses to reduce their environmental impact, improve energy efficiency, and optimize resource use. Through this in-depth analysis, the study aims to provide practical insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by companies in the green economy transition, offering valuable lessons for other businesses and policymakers. Finally, the study uses a comparative approach to analyze the green economy initiatives in Azerbaijan in relation to international best practices and the experiences of other countries. This comparative analysis helps contextualize Azerbaijan's progress within the broader global movement towards sustainable development, identifying areas where the country can improve and align its strategies with global standards and trends.

The combination of these methods – literature review, quantitative analysis, qualitative interviews, case studies, and comparative analysis – provides a comprehensive approach to understanding the transformation of production systems in the context of the green economy, with a particular focus on Azerbaijan's efforts to implement sustainable development principles.

3. Results

In general, the green economy is a model of economic development that is focused on sustainable development, which considers environmental, social, and economic aspects. The main goals of the green economy are to reduce environmental damage, increase resource efficiency, and improve people's quality of life. This concept arose as a response to the problems of the traditional economy, which often leads to the depletion of natural resources, environmental pollution, and social inequality; its use is possible in any field: chemical, agricultural, industrial, etc⁹⁻¹¹).

The main principles of this approach are: reducing carbon emissions by switching to low-carbon technologies and energy sources (solar, wind, hydropower, and biomass), efficient use of natural resources, waste minimisation and recycling; protection and restoration of ecosystems, sustainable management of natural resources; ensuring equal access to resources, creating green jobs, and improving working conditions; stable economic development; reduction of risks associated with climate

change and resource depletion; support and development of new technologies that contribute to sustainable development¹²⁻¹⁴). The use and development of all these components of this approach allows creating favourable conditions for economic growth, which not only increases the well-being of society but also preserves the natural environment for future generations (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: The product life cycle in eco-design

Notably, there is more than one approach describing how sustainable development goals should be achieved. Therewith, the green economy approach differs from other approaches to achieving sustainable development goals, such as the circular economy, primarily in its emphasis and approach to solving environmental and economic problems. The circular economy is a concept of economic development focused on the sustainable use of resources and waste minimisation¹⁵). Its main principle is to move from the traditional linear model of consumption and production (resource extraction, production, consumption, waste disposal) to a closed cycle, where the waste of exhausted consumption is returned back to the production process as secondary resources or energy. Unlike a linear economy, where resources are used once and then discarded, the concept aims to maximise the service life of products, reuse them, and return to the production cycle. Thus, some differences can be noted in the approaches of the concepts of “circular economy” and “green economy”^{16,17}). The green economy focuses on economic growth and development, with an emphasis on minimising negative environmental impacts, seeking to integrate the principles of environmental sustainability into economic activities to reduce pollution and improve resource efficiency¹⁸). The circular economy, on the contrary, is focused on eliminating waste and maximising the reuse of resources. The main idea is to use closed production and consumption cycles to minimise the consumption of primary resources and reduce the overall environmental footprint. In terms of measures and tools, the green

economy uses economic measures such as incentives and subsidies for environmentally sustainable technologies and practices. This includes tax incentives, financing and other support measures to encourage the transition to cleaner and more efficient production methods¹⁹). In addition, the green economy and the circular economy are often seen as tools to achieve global goals such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions or improving overall environmental sustainability. They can be applied at various levels – from individual companies to national and international economic policies. Thus, although all these approaches are aimed at achieving sustainable development, each of them has its own unique characteristics and methods, which allows them to be adapted to different economic and social contexts.

In itself, the transformation of production systems is a process of changing and modernising production processes, technologies, and organisational structures to improve the efficiency, product quality, and competitiveness of enterprises^{20,21}). This process may include the introduction of new technologies, changing business models, improving management and automation processes, and adapting to environmental changes such as globalisation and digitalisation^{22,23}). In the context of the implementation of the principles of the green economy, this kind of transformation is aimed at creating sustainable and environmentally friendly production processes that minimise the negative impact on the environment, use resources more efficiently and contribute to long-term sustainable development (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Transformation of production processes in the context of a green economy

Thus, this process itself is quite complex and diverse, which is why it requires additional assessment to optimise it and understand the development possibilities. It is also worth assessing the general state and trends of the state of the ecological environment in Azerbaijan. This is how the situation with water resources was shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Data in the context of water resources management in Azerbaijan in the period from 1990 to 2022

Year	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2013
Water intake from natural water resources, mln m ³	16176	13971	11110	12050	11566	12509
Water consumption, mln m ³	12477	10223	6588	8607	7715	8229
Volume of recycled and recycled water, mln m ³	1628	1696	1875	2224	1787	2184
The ratio of water consumption to water intake, %	77%	73%	59%	71%	67%	66%
The ratio of recycled and recycled water to water intake, %	10%	12%	17%	18%	15%	17%
Year	2016	2019	2020	2021	2022	Change in the indicator, %
Water intake from natural water resources, mln m ³	12504	13227	12961	13743	13841	-14%
Water consumption, mln m ³	8824	9472	9693	10526	10528	-16%
Volume of recycled and recycled water, mln m ³	2346	2358	2243	2795	2653	63%
The ratio of water consumption to water intake, %	71%	72%	75%	77%	76%	-1%
The ratio of recycled and recycled water to water intake, %	19%	18%	17%	20%	19%	90%

Source: compiled by the authors based on data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.⁹⁾

As can be seen from Table 1, the variables have different trends in the country. Thus, the level of water intake from natural resources decreased from 1990 to 2022 at the level of 14%, indicating that the country has begun to use natural resources more efficiently; this is also evidenced by a decrease in water consumption. The increase in the volume of recycled water also indicates an increase in the efficiency of water management approaches: simultaneously, the ratio of recycled water to water intake has increased almost 2 times, which is a good indicator.

To enhance the efficiency of water transportation and reduce losses, it is necessary to implement a series of infrastructural and technological improvements. First, the modernisation and rehabilitation of existing water supply networks should be prioritised. Many water losses occur due to ageing, corroded, or poorly maintained pipelines, which are prone to leakage. Replacing outdated pipes with modern, corrosion-resistant materials, such as high-density polyethylene (HDPE) or ductile iron pipes, could significantly decrease physical water losses. Second, the introduction of smart water management technologies would allow for better monitoring and immediate detection of leakages. For instance, the deployment of real-time monitoring systems using Internet of Things (IoT) sensors can help to promptly identify and localise leaks. Smart

meters, pressure sensors, and automatic control valves can optimise the flow within the network and reduce excess pressure, which is often a key factor contributing to pipe bursts and leakage.

Third, reducing illegal connections and unauthorised water use through stricter regulatory controls and increased surveillance would be important. Illegal tapping not only leads to direct losses but also reduces the overall efficiency and sustainability of water distribution systems. Strengthening the legal framework and investing in public awareness campaigns about the importance of responsible water use can help mitigate this problem. Finally, implementing district metered areas (DMA) in urban water networks can localise leakage detection and pressure management. By dividing the water distribution system into smaller, manageable sectors, it becomes easier to detect discrepancies between inflow and consumption, thus enabling targeted maintenance and repairs. Collectively, these measures can contribute to significantly reducing water losses during transportation, thus enhancing the overall efficiency of water use and supporting sustainable water resource management in Azerbaijan. In addition, it is necessary to evaluate the indicators characterising the safety of treated wastewater and changes in water use efficiency, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Data on safely treated wastewater and changes in water use efficiency in the period from 2016 to 2022

Year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Change
The share of safely treated wastewater, in %	43.6	47	49.2	51.8	52.6	53.3	56.2	29%
Change in water use efficiency over time, USD/m ³	3.7	3.89	4.85	4.58	3.73	4.49	6.57	78%

Source: compiled by the authors based on data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.⁹⁾

Table 2 shows that the share of safely treated wastewater increased from 43.6% to 56.2% (by 12.6 percentage points, or 29%), while the level of water use efficiency increased from 3.7 USD/m³ to 6.57 USD/m³, that is, by 78%. This is

a substantial improvement in the country's quality of water use over such a period of time. The data in the context of pollutant emissions are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Data on the negative impact on the external environment in Azerbaijan

Year	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2013	2016	2019	2020	2021	2022	Change, %
The total amount of pollutants released by stationary sources, thousand tonnes	2913	1033	627	1781	491	282	432	442	420	457	480	-84%
Pollutants from stationary sources were caught and neutralised – total, thousand tonnes	804	154	112	1223	277	84	244	265	274	301	322	-60%
The ratio of captured and neutralised pollutants to the total amount of pollutants, %	28	15	18	69	56	30	56	60	65	66	67	139%
Emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere – total, thousand tonnes	2846	1326	908	1054	957	1137	1170	1122	841	880	930	-67%

Source: compiled by the authors based on data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.⁹⁾

Table 3 shows that total emissions of pollutants decreased by 84%, while captured and neutralised substances decreased by 60%: this led to an increase in the ratio of captured and neutralised substances to the total amount of

pollutants. Thus, only 33% of pollutants currently enter the external environment. The data in the waste context is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Data in the context of waste in the Republic of Azerbaijan from 2000 to 2022

Year	2000	2003	2006	2009	2012	2015	2017	2019	2020	2021	2022	Change
Total amount of waste	1236	2378	2441	2284	3097	2350	2676	3256	3452	3778	3985	222%
Amount of waste per capita, kg	153	286	283	255	333	244	272	328	345	376	395	1

Source: compiled by the authors based on data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.⁴⁾

As can be seen from Table 4, the total amount of waste (both total and per capita) in the country is increasing, which indicates that there are still problems in this area, despite all attempts to reduce emissions.

Azerbaijan is actively working on the transition to a green economy, taking an integrated approach to sustainable development and reducing dependence on oil; an important part of this strategy is to increase the share of renewable energy sources in electricity production by a third by 2030. Azerbaijan is also taking steps to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In 2024, Baku hosted the 29th United Nations (UN) Climate Change Conference (COP29), which underscored Azerbaijan's significance in global efforts to combat climate change and promote sustainable energy. This event served as a step toward attracting international investment and supporting economic growth beyond the oil sector⁶⁾.

As already mentioned, the transformation of production systems is a fairly large-scale and comprehensive process. However, in the context of the transition to the principles

of a “green” economy, it has its own characteristics, especially considering the current situation in Azerbaijan. Notably, it is possible to provide a fairly large number of recommendations on exactly what this process should be, given its versatility. However, the study identified only the main ones among them. Thus, a qualitative approach is to introduce more energy-efficient equipment: for example, high-efficiency motors (IE3 and IE4); variable frequency drives; LED lighting; energy-efficient heating, ventilation, and air conditioning systems; energy-efficient pumps and compressors, etc. Thus, companies in the industrial sector, in conditions of the existence of such opportunities, can replace old electric motors with new ones, already more “green” from the beginning of work. In addition, an important approach is the optimisation of resource management, which includes both the management of water resources and waste, energy, used materials, etc. To ensure the long-term sustainability of its water management practices amid the challenges posed by climate change and population growth, Azerbaijan must

adopt an integrated water resources management (IWRM) approach that combines infrastructure modernisation, institutional reform, and technological innovation^{15),16)}. Key strategies should include the development of climate-resilient water infrastructure, enhancement of wastewater treatment and reuse systems, and expansion of data-driven monitoring networks for real-time management of water resources. Furthermore, promoting water-saving technologies in agriculture – such as drip irrigation – and encouraging efficient water use through public awareness campaigns are essential to reducing consumption. At the policy level, aligning national strategies with international frameworks, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 6), and strengthening transboundary water cooperation with neighbouring countries can also play a pivotal role⁶⁾. While Azerbaijan has initiated several water sectors reforms and pilot projects focused on water reuse and conservation, scaling these efforts and ensuring consistent investment in adaptive capacity will be crucial to addressing water scarcity over the coming decades.

Thus, in the context of optimising production systems at enterprises, an effective approach is to form such management methods that would increase the efficiency of using a large list of resources; while having government support (through any programmes) would also be a substantial advantage. The same applies to waste management, which must be applied both from the standpoint of introducing new technologies but also at the logistics level for more efficient and successful waste transfer to the desired territories. In addition, it is effective to introduce initiatives on recycling and subsequent recycling of waste^{24),25)}.

Within the framework of the same concept, an eco-design approach can be used – this is the process of creating products considering their environmental impact at all stages of the life cycle, from development and production to recycling. Its essence is to minimise the use of materials, raw materials, while using materials that are renewable. In addition, manufactured products should be designed for as long a period of time as possible, be energy efficient, and minimise waste. Digitalisation and automation are key elements of the transformation of production systems in a green economy.^{26),27)} This includes the introduction of Big Data technology, which allows collecting and analysing large amounts of data and predicting the occurrence of various events in the future; the creation of virtual models of production processes and equipment for testing and optimisation without the need to stop production, and using them to manage all stages of the product lifecycle, from development to disposal; the use of robots to perform repetitive tasks such as assembly, welding and packaging; they can also be used in other areas, for example, logistics. External factors such as international sanctions, geopolitical tensions, and global economic fluctuations can significantly hinder the implementation of green

economy policies in Azerbaijan by limiting access to foreign investment, advanced technologies, and international markets for green products and services. Sanctions or regional conflicts may disrupt trade routes and inflows of financial or technical support essential for launching large-scale green infrastructure projects. Moreover, economic instability can divert national priorities and public funding away from long-term sustainability goals toward more immediate socio-economic concerns. To mitigate these challenges, Azerbaijan can adopt a multi-layered strategy focused on strengthening domestic capabilities and diversifying partnerships. This includes investing in local innovation ecosystems and promoting the development of homegrown green technologies, reinforcing regional cooperation for resource sharing and technical exchange, and engaging in international climate finance mechanisms, such as the Green Climate Fund. Additionally, fostering resilient public-private partnerships can serve as a buffer against external shocks by pooling financial, operational, and intellectual resources to maintain progress toward green transition goals regardless of geopolitical uncertainty. These strategies, combined with institutional reforms and transparent governance, would help Azerbaijan sustain its environmental policy commitments even in a volatile global environment.

Notably, to achieve any results in this direction, there must be a relationship between government authorities and representatives of enterprises. There must be cooperation between these entities to create sufficiently good conditions for the implementation of the principles of the “green economy at enterprises”, which is generally quite difficult to achieve, although it is worth striving for. Nevertheless, the main initiatives should be directed by the state. They should consist of: promoting energy efficiency and renewable energy sources through the use of tools such as subsidies, tax incentives, low-rate loans; improving waste management and subsequent recycling (through the formation of appropriate programmes); supporting innovative development; improving the investment climate in the country, etc.

4. Discussion

The main goal of the “green economy” is to reduce environmental damage, increase resource efficiency, and improve the quality of life (social aspect). Approaches to reduce carbon emissions are used to do this, such as using resources efficiently, minimising waste, protecting the environment, ensuring equal access to resources, creating appropriate jobs, and achieving economic stability. Therewith, this approach focuses on minimising environmental impacts and improving resource efficiency, while the circular economy focuses on waste disposal and resource reuse. Both approaches support sustainable

development but use different strategies. In turn, the transformation of production systems in accordance with the principles of the green economy includes the introduction of energy-efficient technologies, optimisation of resource management, promotion of eco-design and integration of digitalisation and automation. Azerbaijan is currently actively implementing approaches related to the “green” economy at its enterprises by increasing the use of renewable energy sources and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The country is striving to achieve sustainable development by substantially improving water management and pollutant emissions but problems in waste management persist²⁸⁾. However, achieving these goals is possible only in the case of more active interaction between public authorities and private entrepreneurs.

Within the framework of the current study, a lot of attention was paid to the concept of the “green economy” as such, but only from the environmental side. The main focus was on how the use of this concept allows improving the state of the external environment, although the socio-economic components of the concept were not noted. The detrimental impact of unsustainable economic growth on the environment was assessed by S.M. Khoshnava et al.,²⁹⁾ emphasising the role of green economic policies in mitigating environmental degradation while promoting social well-being, equity, and economic prosperity. The researchers also recommended focusing on green economy strategies that solve environmental problems and achieve sustainable development as the main drivers of sustainable development, with public well-being as a secondary consideration. They emphasised that the state authorities should form only such long-term development goals within the framework of the concept of a “green economy” that will allow maintaining a decent standard of living for citizens, ensuring their well-being, and enabling the economy to develop in the long term. The potential of the green economy to mitigate environmental, economic, and social risks while increasing overall sustainability was assessed by E.B. Ali et al.³⁰⁾ The authors noted that the use of this concept truly allows achieving the sustainable development goals in the country much more effectively, but for this, solving social and institutional problems, including corruption, improving the situation in the field of education and the quality of functioning of the area of production of the latest technologies, and the priority of practical implementation of the green policy economies beyond contractual obligations, is necessary. Although the study on the introduction of the “green” economy did not place much emphasis on this, notably, environmental and social components should also be considered by both the government and enterprises when forming a long-term development policy within the framework of the “green economy” concept.

It was mentioned in the paper that the transition to the principles of a “green” economy is quite difficult,

including due to the need for interaction between public authorities and the private sector. The transition to a green economy and the challenges in technological change to ensure sustainable development were evaluated by P. Soderholm³¹⁾. The researcher stated that understanding socio-technical transitions requires cooperation between natural scientists, engineers, and sociologists. Closer interaction between economics, management, and political science can improve the understanding of company incentives and socio-technical systems in management research, and the integration of green business perspectives and innovation can reduce uncertainty in standard business scenarios³²⁾. Therewith, innovations should be introduced in both the private and public sectors; in addition, all initiatives aimed at moving to more “green” approaches should be directed by the political authorities. Thus, the conclusions made in the framework of the study generally confirm the results obtained in this paper: interaction between public authorities and the private sector is an important part of achieving the principles of the “green economy” and sustainable development. It is possible to reach mutual understanding in this direction only if the initiative comes from both sides, although it is worth agreeing that it should be directed primarily by the state authorities. This is caused at least by the fact that, from the standpoint of theory, the goal of the enterprise is to maximise its own profit and not social welfare and the state of the external environment. Although in practice, this is not entirely true since companies also benefit by adhering to sustainable development goals (investors can invest more actively in companies of this kind, just as citizens consume their products more actively), however, this does not change the fact that ensuring the social and other needs of citizens is the prerogative of the state.

The main problems associated with the possibilities of pro-ecological economic transformation and the introduction of the principles of sustainable development into the economy were described in their paper by W. Jakubczak et al.³³⁾ The researchers noted that sustainable, environmentally friendly economic development, consistent with the principles of a green economy and funded by green financing, is a new and important idea for the 21st century, which became especially evident after the outbreak of the COVID-19 crisis. The study emphasised the need to implement the principles of sustainable development to mitigate the adverse effects of the development of civilisation associated with environmental pollution, reduced biodiversity, etc. The study on the situation in Azerbaijan also noted various difficulties in achieving a better state of the external environment, and among them, the problems of financing are also notable. They are especially relevant for Azerbaijan, as there are internal opportunities to finance large projects, which include investments in the latest technologies to reduce the negative impact on the external environment. Thus, the

state authorities should create conditions for attracting external investments.

The green economy, circular economy, and bioeconomics were also compared in terms of their potential for global sustainability by D. D'Amato and J. Korhonen³⁴). The authors concluded that these three approaches together highlight the need for a global society and economy based on renewable, biodiversity-friendly processes that meet current and future economic and social needs. However, if these approaches are implemented without considering the global sustainability of the network, they may lead to unintended consequences, which will not solve the difficulties that arise in the context of achieving sustainable development goals. The study recommends the development of coordinated decision-making strategies at enterprises and in the state apparatus to improve practical implementation. The assessment of approaches typical of a cyclical economy was conducted by A. Chizaryfard et al.³⁵) Researchers have noted that a cyclical economy is a concept that allows simultaneously achieving a better level of economic development at a low rate of deterioration in the quality of the external environment. Material flows within the framework of using the concept are dynamic and multidirectional, which is largely influenced by how accessible resources are. As part of the current study, it was also concluded that these concepts have some differences, although they generally achieve the same goal. Thus, all of them can be used in symbiosis to get even better results.

5. Conclusions

Thus, within the framework of the study, it was concluded that the transition to a green economy is a key strategy for sustainable development, harmonising environmental, social and economic aspects: this model eliminates the shortcomings of the traditional economy, allowing the solutions to inequality and environmental pollution. The concept of a "green" economy, which, in comparison with a circular economy, focuses on integrating environmental sustainability into economic growth, allows success substantially. The green economy uses economic incentives, subsidies, and supportive policies to encourage the adoption of cleaner technologies and efficient production methods, contributing to a sustainable transition in various sectors of the economy.

The paper showed that Azerbaijan has demonstrated substantial progress in managing its water resources, improving water use efficiency and waste management methods. This is shown by the statistical data that described the state of the country in the context of water resources management and in the field of environmental conditions. Despite all this, Azerbaijan faces constant problems, especially in the field of waste management. The total volume of waste generated continues to grow, which requires further efforts to reduce waste and recycle

and restore resources. The country is actively working to integrate renewable energy sources into its energy mix, aiming to increase the share of renewable energy sources to one-third by 2030. The country's commitment to achieving the principles of sustainable development is confirmed by the holding of the 29th UN Climate Change Conference in Baku.

The study concluded that the transformation of production systems towards a green economy in Azerbaijan requires an integrated approach, including the introduction of energy-efficient technologies, optimisation of resource management, and promotion of eco-design principles. The introduction of advanced technologies can substantially reduce energy consumption in industrial operations, which will positively affect the country's ability to achieve sustainable development goals. Digitalisation and automation of the main processes at enterprises will also help in this. The use of big data, virtual models, and robotics will allow optimising production processes, reducing resource consumption, and increasing overall efficiency. Nevertheless, to achieve these goals, interaction between government agencies and entrepreneurs remains important. Further research is relevant to assess the possibility of introducing the latest technologies at individual enterprises and in the context of the state administration apparatus to ensure a more effective transition to the principles of a green economy in Azerbaijan.

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